

Metaverse of Observational Astronomy and Public Datasets of Observational Data.

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Abstract:

A Metaverse as a point cloud for visual photometry is generated from a combination of drone, telescope and mobile images using VSLAM telemetry and photometry technologies, to create a Metaverse with many applications, ranging from public data sets for data mining phenomenological models to navigational uses and dark sky maps.

Images are saved as NFTs to generate a Metaverse, and mined to create a point cloud stored on a blockchain web3 and web2 storage systems, commonly called cloud storage as publicly published data sets,

In this paper we propose two such observational schedules using naked eye observation, drone imaging and observation on various telescopes in the Indian subcontinent.

The first schedule consists of imaging possible exoplanet candidates from the TESS database, and the second schedule of Supernovae candidates based on a filter using a decision tree on the linear sky survey data and published information on Supernovae predictions.

Keywords: VSLAM, Point Cloud, Photometry, Metaverse, 3D Point Cloud, IPFS, FileCoin, Azure, Supernovae, NFT, drone, mobile.

<what>Automated logging system for public datasets on github for telescope, drone and mobile data, interactive stitching to a 3D open cloud and persistence to cloud and NFT based tokenization for metaverse creation. </what>

<how>Use of Github based Codebase with scripts for NFT creation, OpenSFM for interactive 3D Point Cloud creation, docker devops of openSFM and persistence to Blob based Azure Cloud Storage and eventual publication with streaming from a Azure Open Dataset to most AR/VR/Web browsers </how>

<why> Open datasets for collaborative research and education on the metaverse. Fallback system for loss of GPS in autonomous navigation systems and quantum GPS systems. </why>

Summary:

Automated logging system for public datasets on github for telescope, drone and mobile data, interactive stitching to a 3D open cloud and persistence to cloud and NFT based tokenization for metaverse creation. Integrations with Microsoft Mesh for viewing using VR glassed, AltSpaceVR, light tables and projection wall displays. Applications to path planning with SLAM and point cloud in lieu of GPS and Quantum GPS systems.

Applications: VTOL Autopilot Stage II Systems.

Code Base: CodeBase and Image Repository.

<https://github.com/stpaul2coderdojo/Pointcloud-for-Vainu-Bappu-Telescope>

Introduction.

Quantum GPS systems show promise with path planning in low altitude VTOL systems, with poor GPS connectivity, in this paper we present a SLAM based 3D point cloud generation and photogrammetry for a robust solution to autonomous flight with tangible reconstruction of visual portals and a metaverse with interactive widgets for astrophysics research and education and an AI business case for increased applicability of data mining and machine learning in astronomy.

Problem Definition.

1. Automated logging of Drone, Mobile and Telescope images for Metaverse creation with NFTs and 3D Point Cloud information and links to datasets on the astronomical object.
2. CodeBase for interactive point cloud creation.

Background.

Photogrammetry involves the creation of three dimensional mesh objects from a series of images combined from various sources, ranging from space and ground telescope imaging to drone imaging and mobile imagery.¹

Traditionally VSLAM or simultaneous localization and mapping has been used for precise photometry and telemetry applications, useful both in reconstructable

3D point clouds, navigation, path planning and in the creation of the metaverse for augmented, virtual, two dimensional and immersive holodeck like experiences, also called a Planetarium in layman's terms. The Metaverse integrates existing Astronomical AI endeavors and forms a portal based UI to sky survey data, including the recent Sloan Sky Survey and the existing corpus of astronomical object datasets.

AutoPilot Stage II definitions, include the use of satellite positioning constellations for precise drone positioning. In this paper we extend the positioning with a 3D point cloud of astronomical object information. SLAM based positioning is increasingly replacing dependency on GPS based systems in low altitude autonomous flight planning.²

Case Study I: Exo Planet Visual Observation.

A list of exoplanet candidates are mined from the TESS survey³ for data mining, an observation schedule is generated for high resolution imaging of the target objects stitched with mobile images and drone imagery using photogrammetry software.⁴ OpenSFM is a photogrammetry tool used in this paper for 3D point cloud creation and persistence.

Case Study II : Imaging Supernovae candidates.

A decision tree based filter is created to list possible supernova candidates using ongoing filters for probability estimation and the creation of an observation schedule for several such objects from linear sky data. Similar to the previous case study, high resolution telescope images are stitched into the point cloud, for a Metaverse of navigable objects and UI object meshes.

Machine Learning Models.

SLAM based pose, localization and point cloud generation from various data streams, including space telescopes, robotic telescopes, all sky camera, drone imagery, and mobile imagery using the OpenSFM application.

Scripts to generate NFTs ⁵from all image assets, IPFS and Azure/Github based persistence.

Minty is an open-source tool that allows users to mint non-fungible tokens (NFTs) on the Ethereum blockchain. The tool was created by the Minty team and is available on GitHub for anyone to use. Minty is built using the Solidity programming language and is compatible with popular Ethereum wallets like MetaMask. The tool allows users to create and customize NFTs with different properties like images, metadata, and royalty fees. Users can also set the number of NFTs to be minted and the price for each NFT. Minty uses a smart contract to handle the creation and management of NFTs, ensuring that they are secure and tamper-proof. Overall, Minty is a powerful

tool for anyone looking to create and sell NFTs on the Ethereum blockchain.⁶

IPFS (InterPlanetary File System) is a distributed peer-to-peer network protocol designed to provide a decentralized and content-addressable method of storing and sharing hypermedia in a distributed file system. IPFS was created by Juan Benet, and the first version was released in 2015. The protocol works by assigning a unique content-based hash to each file or piece of data, which is used to address and locate the data on the network. IPFS can be used for a variety of purposes, including website hosting, data storage, and distribution of files and media.

Filecoin is a decentralized storage network built on top of IPFS. It was created by Juan Benet and the team at Protocol Labs, the same team behind IPFS. Filecoin aims to create a global marketplace for storage, where users can rent out their unused storage space to other users who need it. Filecoin uses a unique proof-of-storage consensus mechanism, where miners provide storage space and bandwidth to the network and earn Filecoin tokens in exchange. The more storage a miner provides, the more tokens they can earn.

Filecoin is designed to solve some of the challenges faced by centralized cloud storage providers, such as high costs, limited capacity, and security risks. By leveraging the decentralized nature of IPFS, Filecoin provides a more secure, efficient, and cost-effective way of storing and sharing data. With Filecoin, users can trust that their data is stored securely and is always available, even in the event of a network outage or other disruption.

OpenSFM (Open Source Structure from Motion) is a popular open-source software library that is used to reconstruct 3D models from 2D images. It has been widely used in the field of astronomical AI due to its ability to handle large datasets and produce accurate 3D point clouds. One of the salient algorithms used in OpenSFM is the Bundle Adjustment algorithm, which is used to optimize the camera parameters and the 3D point locations to produce the most accurate 3D model possible.

Another algorithm used in OpenSFM is the Sequential Estimation algorithm, which is used to estimate the 3D structure of the scene from the image data. This algorithm is particularly useful for astronomical AI applications as it can handle noisy data and produce high-quality 3D models.

OpenSFM is considered one of the best algorithms for a 3D point cloud for astronomical AI due to its ability to handle large datasets and produce highly accurate results. It has been used in a variety of astronomical AI applications, including the creation of 3D models of galaxies and the reconstruction of planetary surfaces. Additionally, OpenSFM is open-source, which means that researchers can modify and adapt the software to meet their specific needs.

Overall, OpenSFM is a powerful tool for astronomical AI researchers looking to create accurate 3D models from large datasets. Its ability to handle noisy data and produce high-quality results make it a valuable asset for a wide range of astronomical AI applications.

Fig 1: Iterative Telescopic Image Acquisition for optimal Point Cloud Generation.

OpenSFM, with the BA algorithm, for a given ROI, allows for an interactive generation of an optimal point cloud by the addition of required high resolution imagery to the dataset, by interactive prompting.

AI Business Model.

Metaverse models with the 3D point cloud render a ready platform using integrated AR/VR and projection/ web displays for an open source portal to metadata and streamable mesh information for interactive education and research.

Professional datasets for autonomous navigation for AutoPilot Stage II systems can be created from several of the public datasets and portal datasets for business applications to supplement ongoing efforts at Quantum GPS and communication systems.

Public Data Sets.

An Azure Open Dataset is created for AltSpace integration of the Metaverse Public Data Set using Microsoft Mesh.⁷

On demand streamed conversion to mesh formats like obj or glb for Microsoft Mesh imports and publication on AltSpaceVR. Light Tables and projective wall systems with DLP projectors are another immersive or non immersive Metaverse application with widgets for an interactive metaverse, apart from traditional two dimensional display viewing on mobile or stationary computing.

The public dataset is directly amenable to streaming with Microsoft Mesh in formats acceptable to an interactive metaverse for educational and research use cases and data mining applications.

Best Practices with OpenSfM imaging.

Here are some best practices for using OpenSfM based on both GitHub documentation and published literature:⁸⁹

1. Image Quality: Ensure that images are of high quality, with good contrast and sharpness. Avoid images with large amounts of noise or blur, as these can negatively affect the quality of the point cloud.
2. Image Overlap: Overlap between images is important for generating accurate 3D point clouds. Ensure that each image has a sufficient overlap with other images in the set.
3. Camera Calibration: Camera calibration is crucial for accurate 3D reconstruction. Ensure that your camera calibration parameters are accurate and up-to-date. OpenSfM provides several calibration tools to help with this process.
4. Bundle Adjustment: Bundle adjustment is a critical step in refining the camera parameters and improving the quality of the 3D point cloud. Be sure to run bundle adjustment on your dataset after feature extraction.
5. Feature Extraction: OpenSfM uses feature extraction algorithms to identify key points in the images for 3D reconstruction. Ensure that your feature extraction parameters are set correctly, and consider using multiple feature extraction algorithms to improve results.
6. Memory Management: OpenSfM can be memory-intensive, especially when processing large datasets. Ensure that you have enough RAM available to avoid out-of-memory errors.
7. Ground Control Points: Ground control points (GCPs) can be used to improve the accuracy of the 3D reconstruction, especially when using a drone or other aerial platform. Ensure that your GCPs are accurately placed and well-distributed throughout the dataset.
8. Iterative Refinement: OpenSfM allows for iterative refinement of the 3D point cloud. Consider running multiple passes of the reconstruction and refinement process to improve the quality of the output.
9. Output Formats: OpenSfM supports several output formats for 3D point

clouds, including PLY, LAS, and OBJ. Choose the output format that best suits your needs.

10. Documentation and Community Support: OpenSfM has an active community of users and developers who can provide assistance and advice. Be sure to consult the documentation and forums for best practices and troubleshooting tips.

Computational Complexity of the OpenSfM Algorithm.

The computational complexity of OpenSfM algorithms can vary depending on the specific algorithm being used and the size of the input data. Here is a general overview of the computational complexity of some of the core algorithms used in OpenSfM:¹⁰

1. Feature detection and matching: The complexity of feature detection and matching depends on the algorithm used. SIFT (Scale-Invariant Feature Transform) and SURF (Speeded-Up Robust Features) algorithms, which are commonly used in OpenSfM, have a time complexity of $O(N \log N)$ and $O(N)$, respectively, where N is the number of keypoints detected in the image.
2. Bundle adjustment: Bundle adjustment is an iterative optimization process used to refine the camera poses and 3D point positions. The computational complexity of bundle adjustment is generally $O(N^3)$, where N is the

number of camera poses and 3D points being optimized.

3. Structure from motion: Structure from motion is the process of estimating the 3D structure of a scene from a sequence of 2D images. The computational complexity of structure from motion depends on the number of images being processed and the complexity of the feature matching and bundle adjustment steps.
4. Depth map estimation: Depth map estimation is the process of estimating the depth of each pixel in an image. The computational complexity of depth map estimation can be quite high, particularly for dense depth estimation methods such as stereo matching or multi-view stereo. These methods typically have a complexity of $O(N^3)$ or higher, where N is the number of pixels in the image.

In terms of space storage complexity, OpenSfM requires storage for the input images, the intermediate feature detection and matching results, and the final 3D point cloud and camera poses. The amount of storage required depends on the number and resolution of the input images, the number of features detected, and the complexity of the scene being reconstructed. For example, a scene with many features and high-resolution images will require more storage than a scene with fewer features and lower-resolution images.

Discussion.

A proposal for the creation of a Metaverse Portal with two case studies of dataset creation and portal integration in the case of Astronomical AI for the data mining of exoplanets, and supernova candidates and estimation of a habitation index and prediction of future supernova events.

The 3D point cloud has found several applications in regenerating arbitrary resolution imagery and data for astronomical phenomenology. It is possible to generate false-colored imagery and extract data from the point cloud for further analysis. The point cloud data can also be used to create 3D meshes for mixed reality applications and online planetariums. This has been demonstrated in projects like OpenSpace, an open-source platform for visualizing astronomical data. The point cloud data can also be streamed on-demand, enabling real-time exploration of astronomical objects.

In drone navigation, the use of SLAM (Simultaneous Localization and Mapping) based navigation with the point cloud has become popular. The drone can use the point cloud data to create a map of the environment and localize itself within that map in real-time. This technique has been applied in various applications such as agriculture, inspection, and search and rescue missions. For example, a project called "Using Point Clouds for Precision Agriculture" demonstrated the use of a drone equipped with LiDAR sensors and OpenSfM to generate high-resolution maps

of crops. These maps were used to optimize irrigation, fertilizer application, and other factors for better crop yields. Another example is the use of point cloud data for building inspections and maintenance, where drones equipped with LiDAR sensors can create detailed 3D maps of buildings to identify potential structural issues.

Future Work.

Expansion of the Metaverse with observational data in interactive generation of the point cloud for reconstruction of arbitrarily high fidelity images for viewing and navigation, with custom automated requisition of images from space telescopes like the Hubble and robotic telescopes.

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